

Synthesis, characterisation, thermal stability and antimicrobial activities of transition metal complexes of plumbagin and its azo derivatives

V. K. Rema Devi^a, Annette Fernandez^{b*} and Annie George^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. Arts College, Trivandrum-695 014, Kerala, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, College of Engineering, Trivandrum-695 016, Kerala, India

E-mail : ann_ambattu@yahoo.co.in

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. College for Women, Trivandrum-695 014, Kerala, India

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Abstract : Plumbagin, 2-methyl-5-hydroxy-1,4-naphthaquinone (HPb) was extracted from air-dried roots of the plant *Plumbago zeylanica*. Two of its azo derivatives, namely 8-(phenylazo)plumbagin (HPAP) and 8-(4'-azoantipyrine)plumbagin (HAAPP) were synthesized and were characterized using UV-Vis, IR and NMR spectral techniques. The complexes of plumbagin and its azo derivatives were synthesized with transition metal ions such as Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III}. These complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance measurements, magnetic moment values, UV-Vis, IR and ESR spectral techniques. Thermogravimetric analysis of [Cr(HAAPP)Cl₃] was carried out and its kinetic parameters such as activation energy 'E', pre-exponential factor 'A' and entropy of activation ΔS* were evaluated using Coats-Redfern equation. HPb, HAAPP and their Cu^{II} complexes were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal properties.

Keywords : Extraction, synthesis, characterization, thermal stability, antimicrobial activity, transition metal complexes.

Introduction

Quinones and their substituted derivatives have been known to possess numerous chemically and biologically significant properties with many important applications in several areas¹⁻³. Naphthaquinone and its derivatives have been used in industry, medicines, and in qualitative and quantitative estimations of metal ions⁴⁻⁶. Naphthaquinones bearing at least one phenolic OH group are potent inhibitors of topoisomerase enzymes⁴. The ability of these ligands to complex divalent metal ions such as Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Mg^{II} parallels their topoisomerase inhibition property and is thought to be the underlying mechanism of their anticancer activity⁴. Plumbagin (HPb) is a highly bioactive compound exhibiting anticancer, antitumour, antibacterial, antifungal, antifeedant, insecticidal and molluscicidal activities⁷⁻¹¹. Interaction of plumbagin with metals has been studied and was found to act as an anionic bidentate ligand forming 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes¹²⁻¹⁴. There are very few reports on the studies of plumbagin directly isolated from the plant and used for the preparation of metal complexes. To the best of our knowledge

studies on the azo derivatives of plumbagin and their complexes have not been reported so far. Hence in this investigation, plumbagin was extracted from *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn. and two of its azo derivatives were synthesized. They were used as ligands to synthesize complexes of metal ions such as Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III}. They were characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic moment values, UV-Vis, IR and ESR spectral techniques. Studies on the thermal decomposition and antimicrobial properties of ligands and a few selected complexes are also reported in this investigation.

Results and discussion

Plumbagin extracted from the plant was obtained as orange crystals with melting point 78 °C and HPAP and HAAPP were obtained as brown and greenish yellow crystals with melting points 110 °C and 114 °C, respectively

Structure of the ligands :

The structures of the ligands were established by UV,

Table 1. IR spectral (cm^{-1}) data with peak assignments of the complexes of HPb, HPAP and HAAPP

Complex	IR spectral frequencies									
	ν_{OH} coord. water	ν_{OH} (phenolic)	ν_{CO} free	ν_{CO} hydrogen- bonded	ν_{CO} chelated	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic)	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$
HPb	-	3350	1660	1644	-	-	1231	-	-	-
Cu(Pb) ₂	-	-	1656	-	1630	-	1242	-	455	-
Ni(Pb) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	3453	-	1657	-	1630	-	1251	-	435	-
Co(Pb) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	3515	-	1655	-	1633	-	1243	-	426	-
Fe(Pb) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)	3420	-	1652	-	1631	-	1240	-	434	350
Cr(Pb) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)	3412	-	1655	-	1633	-	1240	-	459	345
HPAP	-	3370	1650	1640	-	1490	1230	-	-	-
Cu(HPAP) ₂ Cl ₂	-	3365	-	1640	1632	1480	1235	560	485	300
Ni(HPAP) ₂ SO ₄	-	3372	-	1645	1630	1481	1234	540	450	-
Co(HPAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	-	3365	-	1640	1631	1481	1232	534	446	-
[Fe(HPAP)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O]	3425	3363	-	1640	1632	1480	1230	565	456	345
[Cr(HPAP) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	-	3365	-	1645	1631	1479	1230	560	460	355
HAAPP	-	3365	1660, 1653	1640	-	1510	1231	-	-	-
[Cu(HAAPP)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O]	3527	3364	-	1640	1635	1490	1233	568	486	290
[Ni(HAAPP)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O]	3427	3367	-	1641	1632	1490	1234	540	450	-
[Co(HAAPP)NO ₃ .H ₂ O]	3428	3368	-	1642	1631	1494	1233	536	448	-
[Fe(HAAPP)Cl ₃]	-	3368	-	141	1610	1491	1236	560	456	350
[Cr(HAAPP)Cl ₃]	-	3369	-	1640	1612	1490	1237	560	465	345

IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. UV-Vis spectrum of HPb shows absorbance at λ_{max} 290, 301 and 367 nm which are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (benzenoid) and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (quinonoid) transitions, respectively. In addition to these, the azo derivatives also gave a band around 320 nm due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the azo group. The IR spectrum of HPb displayed a broad peak at 3350 cm^{-1} due to the presence of hydrogen-bonded OH group. Strong peaks at 1664 and 1644 cm^{-1} showed a free carbonyl and hydrogen-bonded carbonyl group respectively. A band at 1231 cm^{-1} is assigned to phenolic C-O stretching absorption. In addition to the peaks in HPb, IR spectra (Table 1) of its azo compounds HPAP and HAAPP showed peaks at 1490 and 1510 cm^{-1} respectively due to the stretching vibration of N=N group. They also exhibited peaks at 759 and 697 cm^{-1} , of mono-substituted benzene ring. HAAPP gave strong peak at 1653 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of pyrazolone ring.

Table 2 gives ¹H NMR spectral data of HPb, HPAP and HAAPP with peak assignments. ¹H NMR spectral

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data of plumbagin and its azo derivatives

HPb	HPAP	HAAPP	Protons	Assignments
δ	δ	δ		
2.13	2.17		3H, s	CH ₃ protons
		2.23	6H, s	Methyl protons attached to the ring
		3.21	3H, s	N-CH ₃ protons
6.80	6.80	6.80	1H, s	Quinonoid proton
7.18-7.38			3H, m	Naphthyl protons
	7.32	7.33	5H, m	Phenyl protons
	7.50	7.50	2H, d	Naphthyl protons
12.0	12.0	12.0	1H, s	Phenolic proton

data of HPb gave a singlet at δ 12 (1H, s) which is due to a phenolic proton. The three phenyl protons in the ring gave a multiplet at δ 7.2-7.3 (3H, m). Proton in the quinonoid ring is obtained as a singlet at δ 6.8. Three-proton singlet at δ 2.1 is due to the protons of the side chain methyl group^{21,22}. The NMR spectrum of HPAP showed

peaks between δ 7.3–7.5 (7H, m) corresponding to five phenyl protons of aniline and two that of the naphthalene ring respectively. In case of HAAPP, resonance at δ 2.2 (6H, s) have been attributed to the two methyl groups, one of HPb and the other of antipyrine ring. The peak at δ 3.2 (3H, s) corresponds to the three protons of N-CH₃ group of antipyrine in the ligand. The quinonoid proton is obtained at δ 6.8 and the naphtholic proton at δ 12 in both HPAP and HAAPP. Thus the coupling occurred at C-8 of HPb, which is particularly the favoured position because of the powerful activating OH group in *para* position at C-5²². The chemical structures of all the three ligands are given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Structure of the metal complexes :

All the complexes of HPb, HPAP and HAAPP are stable, colored and soluble in methanol and chloroform. Analytical and physico-chemical measurement data of the complexes are given in Table 3. The metal to ligand ratio in complexes is found to be 1 : 2 in all complexes of HPb and HPAP except the Fe^{III} complex of HPAP. In the case of HAAPP, the ratio is 1 : 1 for all the complexes. The molar conductance of these complexes are very low in

solvents such as acetonitrile, nitrobenzene and methanol indicating that they are nonelectrolytes except Cr^{III} complex of HPAP. The molar conductivity values of Cr^{III} complex of HPAP is found to be 123, 21 and 90 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile, nitrobenzene and methanol indicating that it is a 1 : 1 electrolyte.

The IR spectra of each ligand were compared with that of corresponding metal complexes in order to confirm the coordination sites of the ligand to the metal ion. The diagnostic IR bands of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The band at 3350 cm^{-1} in HPb disappears in the complexes indicating the involvement of the phenolic OH group in complex formation after deprotonation. The C–O (phenolic) stretching frequency is also shifted to higher energy indicating the coordination through O atom²³. The H-bonded C=O absorption at 1644 cm^{-1} in the ligand is shifted to lower energy in complexes showing its involvement in complex formation. Other relevant peaks of HPb are retained in all the complexes. Non-ligand bands between 500–400 cm^{-1} appear in all the complexes due to M–O stretching vibrations²⁴. Thus HPb behaves as an anionic bidentate OO donor ligand.

In the complexes of HPAP and HAAPP, the ligand bands due to the free carbonyl group shifts to lower energy by 20–30 cm^{-1} which indicates the involvement in coordination. The ligand band at 3370 cm^{-1} (ν_{OH}) remains unchanged in the complexes. In HAAPP the pyrazolone carbonyl at 1653 cm^{-1} is shifted to around 1630 cm^{-1} in all the complexes showing its participation in complexation. The peak at 1640 cm^{-1} is retained in complexes showing that the hydrogen-bonded carbonyl at C-4 is not participating in chelation. The ligand bands due to the $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ also shift to the lower energy by 10 cm^{-1} in all the complexes suggesting the involvement of azo nitrogen in chelation²⁵. Complexes with coordinated water and anions exhibit characteristic bands. Thus HPAP behaves as neutral bidentate ON donor ligand. HAAPP behaves as neutral tridentate ONO donor ligand. This is further confirmed by the presence of M–O and M–N stretching frequencies²⁴.

Electronic spectral data of the complexes of HPb, HPAP and HAAPP with the peak assignments are given in Table 3. These spectral peak assignments suggest four-coordinate square planar geometry for Cu(Pb)₂ and six-coordinate octahedral or distorted octahedral geometry to

Table 3. Analytical and physical measurements data of complexes of HPb, HPAP and HAAPP

Complex	% Composition					Electrolytic nature	Magnetic moment at room temp. (B.M.)	Assignments of electronic spectra (cm ⁻¹)
	C	H	N	Cl/S	Metal			
Cu(Pb) ₂	59.8	3.3	-	-	14.4	Non	1.81	12980 ² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}
Brown	(60.3)	(3.65)			(14.5)	electrolyte		18518 ² B _{1g} → ² E _g
Ni(Pb) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	56.1	3.9	-	-	12.8	Non	3.17	11150 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(56.3)	(3.4)			(12.52)	electrolyte		15200 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) 23780 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P) 30400 charge transfer (c/t)
Co(Pb) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	55.9	3.8	-	-	12.9	Non	5.02	9000 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(56.3)	(3.4)			(12.56)	electrolyte		19200 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) 29900 (c/t)
Fe(Pb) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)	54.4	3.1	-	7.2	11.9	Non	5.2	21500 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
Brown	(54.6)	(3.3)		(7.3)	(11.55)	electrolyte		17000 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} 29500 (c/t)
Cr(Pb) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)	54.9	3.1	-	7.32	11.1	Non	3.9	17360 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}
Black	(55.1)	(2.91)		(7.4)	(10.84)	electrolyte		27395 (c/t)
Cu(HPAP) ₂ Cl ₂	56.1	3.1	7.1	9.7	8.6	Non	1.9	13980 ² E _g → ² T _{2g}
Brown	(56.7)	(3.3)	(7.7)	(9.9)	(8.83)	electrolyte		29550 c/t
Ni(HPAP) ₂ SO ₄	54.8	3.0	7.6	4.1	8.1	Non	3.2	11200 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(55.2)	(3.2)	(7.5)	(4.33)	(7.9)	electrolyte		15220 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) 23500 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)
Co(HPAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	52.2	3.0	10.7	-	7.4	Non	5.1	8700 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(53.2)	(3.12)	(10.9)	-	(7.68)	electrolyte		21000 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
[Fe(HPAP)Cl ₃ .H ₂ O]	44.3	2.6	6.2	23.4	12.3	Non	5.2	20500 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
Brown	(43.1)	(2.5)	(5.9)	(22.6)	(11.8)	electrolyte		17000 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} 29000 (c/t)
[Cr(HPAP) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	54.1	3.3	7.3	14.0	6.8	1 : 1	3.8	17200 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}
Brown	(54.9)	(3.23)	(7.5)	(14.3)	(7.0)			27500 (c/t)
[Cu(HAAPP)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O]	47.2	3.4	10.2	12.9	11.8	Non	1.9	14850 ² E _g → ² T _{2g}
Brown	(47.6)	(3.2)	(10.1)	(12.8)	(11.5)	electrolyte		29550 (c/t)
[Ni(HAAPP)SO ₄ .H ₂ O]	46.1	3.0	9.5	12.8	10.1	Non	3.1	12100 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(45.9)	(3.13)	(9.7)	(12.9)	(10.6)	electrolyte		15500 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) 23750 ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)
[Co(HAAPP)NO ₃ .H ₂ O]	43.6	2.9	13.6	-	9.4	Non	5.02	9500 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)
Brown	(43.8)	(3.0)	(13.9)	-	(9.7)	electrolyte		19900 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
[Fe(HAAPP)Cl ₃]	45.8	3.1	9.8	18.2	10.1	Non	5.19	17000 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g}
Black	(46.8)	(3.2)	(9.9)	(18.8)	(9.9)	electrolyte		20500 ⁶ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g} 29300 (c/t)
[Cr(HAAPP)Cl ₃]	46.9	3.1	9.9	18.8	9.6	Non	3.82	17130 ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}
Black	(47.9)	(3.2)	(10)	(19)	(9.3)	electrolyte		27390 (c/t)

all other complexes of the three ligands. Magnetic moment values and molar conductance measurements also agree with the structures proposed. The tentative struc-

tures proposed are given as in Scheme 2.

ESR spectrum of Cu(Pb)₂ :

The X-band ESR spectrum of the complex is charac-

Scheme 2

teristic of Cu^{II} in axial field symmetry, $g_{||} = g_z$ and $g_{\perp} = g_x = g_y$. Hyperfine splitting is seen in the parallel component with partial overlapping but not in the perpendicular component. $g_{||}$, g_{\perp} and g_{av} , calculated are 2.327, 2.0452 and 2.1861 respectively^{26,27}. The trend $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ observed for the complex shows that the unpaired electron is located in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu^{II} ion and the spectrum obtained is characteristic of axial sym-

metry²⁸⁻³⁰. $A_{||}$ value calculated for the complex is 246 G. Since the hyperfine component shows no hyperfine splitting, $A_{\perp} = 0$ ³¹.

Thermogravimetric studies :

The complex [Cr(HAAPP)Cl₃] was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis (Table 4). The complex showed a two-stage decomposition pattern. The first stage of decomposition took place in the temperature range 455–673 K, with a peak temperature of 643 K. The mass loss corresponds to the removal of azo and carbonyl groups coordinated to the metal ion along with the methyl group, probably of HPb^{23,32}. The second stage, starting from 688–923 K has a peak temperature of 802 K. The mass loss corresponds to the loss of remaining part of the ligand. The final mass loss corresponds to the residue Cr₂O₃. The calculated value of 14% is obtained by independent pyrolysis of the complex. Thus the complex is stable up to 455 K and undergoes two-stage decomposition with peak temperature 643 and 802 K.

The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters were also estimated for each of the well-defined decomposition stage using Coats-Redfern equation³³. The order parameter 'n' in each stage was estimated using a computer program. 'n' is chosen for satisfactory values of correlation coefficient ($\gamma \cong 1$) which indicates near perfect fitness of the results. A plot of $\ln g(\alpha)$ vs $1/T^2$ is made for each decomposition stage, value of activation energy 'E' and pre-exponential factor 'A' were obtained. Entropy of activation ΔS^* was also calculated. The negative value of ΔS^* indicate that activated complexes have more ordered configuration than the reactants and the reactions are slower than normal.

Table 4. Phenomenological and kinetic parameters of the thermal decomposition of the Cr^{III} complex of HAAPP

Complex	Decomposition stage	Peak temp. in DTG (K)	Activation energy (E) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Pre-exponential factor (A) (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation (ΔS^*) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Order parameter 'n'	Peak width (K)	% Mass loss		Mass assignments
								From TG	Calculated	
[Cr(HAAPP)Cl ₃]	I	643	54.854	1.599×10^2	-131.86	2	455-673	18.1	17.8	Azo and carbonyl coordinated and methyl group
	II	802	81.52	5.745×10^2	-140.65	2	688-923	45.0	45.4	Remaining part of the ligand
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.8	14	Residue, Cr ₂ O ₃

Table 5. Antimicrobial activities of HPb, HAAPP and their Cu^{II} complexes

Compd.	Antibacterial activity – Zone of inhibition (mm)							Antifungal activity : (+) no inhibition, (-) inhibition					
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>Kleb. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. Licheniformis</i>	<i>B. brevis</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>P. notatum</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>Rhizopus</i>	<i>Phytophthora</i>	<i>Saccharomyces</i>
HPb	33	21	7	23	30	25	21	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu(Pb) ₂	10	6	6	8	9	6	7	-	-	-	-	-	-
HAAPP	31	7	6	13	27	15	15	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Cu(HAAPP)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O]	11	-	6	10	8	8	7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Norfloxacin (10 µg/disc)	30	31	35	nil	nil	26	nil						
Cephalexin (30 µg/disc)	33	15	6	nil	nil	18	nil						
								Control	+	+	+	+	+

Antimicrobial properties :

The antimicrobial properties of plumbagin have been widely reported by several workers³⁴⁻³⁶. Hence HPb, its azo derivative HAAPP and their Cu^{II} complexes were subjected to antibacterial and antifungal studies as per reported methods. The result of these studies against seven bacteria and six fungi chosen for the study are given in Table 5. It was observed that HPb and HAAPP exhibited high antibacterial activity in all cases except *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The extent of activity of these compounds was comparable to that of standard microbial sensitivity disc, Norfloxacin (10 µg/disc) in all the cases. Cu^{II} complexes of the two ligands also exhibited high antibacterial activity, but less than those of the chelating agents. The lower activities of the complexes than their ligands may be explained on the basis of their low lipid solubility. Thus the metal ion cannot reach the desirable site of action on the cell wall and interfere with the normal cell activity. The nature of metal ion also plays a decisive role in determining the antibacterial properties³⁷.

Antifungal activity studies of these ligands and the complexes showed high fungicidal activity against six fungi. The increased activity can be explained by chelate theory^{38,39}. Chelation reduces polarity on the metal ion in complexes, which increases its hydrophobic character favouring its permeation through the lipid layer of membranes of fungi, Thus it can be concluded that the antimicrobial properties is a combination of several factors such as steric, electronic and pharmo-kinetic factors.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used for the investiga-

tion were of AR grade (BDH/Merck). Chemicals used for antimicrobial studies were of bactograde quality.

Elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) was carried out by micro analytical method at CDRI, Lucknow. Metals in the complexes were estimated as per standard procedures¹⁷. Copper in the complexes was estimated gravimetrically as Cu₂(CNS)₂, nickel as nickel dimethylglyoximate. Cobalt was estimated by precipitating as cobalt pyridine-thiocyanate. Fe^{III} was estimated by direct pyrolysis of the complexes to its oxide. Cr^{III} was estimated by oxidizing it to dichromate by persulphate oxidation and estimating it iodometrically. Sulphur in the complexes was estimated after oxidizing it with concentrated nitric acid in presence of a few drops of perchloric acid to sulphate, which was then determined gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Estimation of chloride was done by decomposing the complexes with Na₂CO₃, excess carbonate was decomposed by nitric acid. Resulting solution was used to estimate chloride volumetrically by Volhard's method.

Molar conductance measurements (Λ) of 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in nitrobenzene, methanol and acetonitrile were made at 300 ± 2 K using a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter type 305, Dip-type conductivity cell with platinum electrode. Magnetic moments of complexes were calculated from magnetic susceptibilities measured by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant.

Electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded using Shimadzu UV-Vis 1601 spectrophotometer in suitable solvents in the range of 200-900 nm. IR spectra of

the ligands and complexes were recorded using discs of KBr on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer between 4000–400 cm^{-1} Proton NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded in CDCl_3 using JEOL-EX 90 FT NMR spectrometer ESR spectrum of Cu^{II} complex was recorded in the solid state at room temperature using DPPH as the standard in a Variant E-4 X-band EPR spectrometer

Thermal (TG and DTG) analysis of the complex were carried out using DuPont 2000 thermal analyzer system in conjunction with a 951 thermogravimetric analyzer with a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and a sample size of 2–3 mg in an atmosphere of static air using a platinum crucible The sample was also subjected to independent pyrolysis by heating for 2 h up to 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until a constant weight was obtained The observed mass losses were compared with those from the TG data

Antibacterial studies were done by disc diffusion method^{18,19} The ligands and their complexes of Cu^{II} were screened for their antibacterial activity against *S aureus*, *E coli*, *B licheniformis*, *B subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella aeruginosa* at a concentration of 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ Antifungal activity of the ligands and their complexes was assayed by incorporating the test solution (1 mg/ml) in SD Agar media against human pathogens, *Penicillium* species, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus* species, plant pathogens, *Rhizopus* species, *Phytophthora* infestans, industrially important *Saccharomyces* species²⁰

Plumbagin was isolated from the air-dried roots of *Plumbago zeylanica* as per the standard procedure¹⁵ The air-dried roots were extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet extractor The crude extract, after removing the solvent, was steam-distilled and the yellow distillate was extracted with chloroform to get plumbagin as orange crystals

Preparation of 8-(phenylazo)plumbagin (HPAP) and 8-(4'-azoantipyridine)plumbagin (HAAPP)

The primary amines used for the preparation of the azo derivatives, HPAP and HAAPP were aniline and 4-aminoantipyridine respectively The amines were diazotized to their respective diazonium chlorides and coupled with HPb in alkaline medium¹⁶ The resulting products obtained were recrystallised from methanol

Synthesis of complexes

Metal ions used were Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} All the complexes were synthesized by adding a solution of the ligand (0.05 M) in ethanol to 0.07 M solution of respective metal salt in aqueous ethanol The mixture was refluxed for about 2–3 h over a water bath It was then concentrated, cooled and the solid separated was suction filtered, washed well with water and then with aqueous ethanol and dried over P_4O_{10} in vacuum

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References

- 1 S Patai, The Chemistry of the Quinonoid Compounds Part 2 Wiley, London, 1974
- 2 R A Morton, 'Biochemistry of Quinones', Academic Press New York, 1965
- 3 M H C Lagorta, *Rev Microbio*, 1983, 14, 11
- 4 Nikhil Gokhale Subhash Padhye Chris Newson and Robin Pritchard, *Metal-Based Drugs* 2000, 7, 121
- 5 A Takashashi and Kambara, *J Polym Sci* 1965, 3, 279
- 6 K Ranganathan Rao and T R Sheshadri, *J Scient and Res*, 1956, 14, 189
- 7 L M V Vijver and A P Lotter *Planta Med* 1971, 20, 8
- 8 I Kubo, M Taniguchi A Chayya and K Tsujimoto *Planta Med Suppl*, 1980
- 9 I Kubo, M Uchida and J A Klocke *Agric Biol Chem* 1983, 47, 911
- 10 I Kubo, J A Klocke, T Matsumoto and T Kami Kawa "IUPAC Pesticide Chemistry, Human Welfare and Environment" eds J Mujamoto, *et al*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1983, 169
- 11 A Marston J D Msonthi and K Hostettmann *Planta Med*, 1984, 50, 279
- 12 L F Fieser *et al*, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1936, 58, 572
- 13 B Venkatappa Rao, Damoder Reddy and M L N Reddy, *Indian J Chem*, Sect A, 1981, 20, 209
- 14 B Venkatappa Rao and M L N Reddy, *J Indian Chem Soc* 1981, 58, 915
- 15 A C Roy and S Dutt, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1928, 5, 419
- 16 F G Mann and B C Saunders *Practical Organic Chemistry*, 4th ed, Orient Longman, 1960, 182
- 17 A I Vogel, *A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, 5th ed, Longman Group, London, 1989

- 18 D Sur-Altiner, E Gurkan, Sarioglu, E Tuzlacı and O Buykbaba, *Fitoterapia*, 1997, **68**, 547
- 19 A Paulo, E T Gomes, A Duarte, S Perret and P J Houghton, *Fitoterapia*, 1997, **68**, 558
- 20 R Vimala, K Sivaprakasham and K Seetharaman, *Madras Agricultural Journal*, 1993, **80:7**, 409
- 21 Sangeeta Bhargava, Manju Agiwal, Sunita Jain, R T Pardasani and Pahup Singh, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 1993, **70**, 234
- 22 B Dinda, G Chel, (Miss) S Saha and A Patra, *Indian J Chem , Sect B*, 1994, **33**, 502
- 23 Prafulla Garge, Subhash Padhye and Jean-Pierre Tuchagues, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 1989, **157**, 239
- 24 Kazuo Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, London, 1963
- 25 L S Mishra, V K Singh and V C Agarwal, *Asian J Chem* , 1992, 333
- 26 M Gordy, "Theory and Application of Electron Spin Resonance", Wiley, New York, 1980
- 27 A Abragam and Bleaney, "Electron Paramagnetic Resonance of Transition Metal Ions", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1970
- 28 G A Renovitch and W A Baker (Jr), *J Am Chem Soc* , 1967, **89**, 6377
- 29 N K Singh, N Aggarwala and R C Aggarwala, *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1984, **23**
- 30 N K Singh, N Aggarwala and R C Aggarwala *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 1985, **24**, 617, 1011
- 31 R H Dunhill, J R Pilbrow and T O Smith, *J Chem Phys* , 1966, **45**, 1474
- 32 M Laila-Kantouri and M Bakola-Christianopoulou, *Thermochim Acta*, 1986, **104**, 39 (Eng)
- 33 A W Coats and J P Redfern, *Nature*, 1964 201
- 34 M J Chan-Bacab and L M Peña-Rodríguez, *Nat Prod Rep* , 2001, **18**, 674
- 35 M A Villavicencio and B E Perez-Escandon, *Folia Entomol Mex* , 1992, **86**, 191
- 36 P U Devi, F E Solomon and A C Sharada, *Indian J Expt Biol* , 1994, **32**, 523
- 37 A Albert, "Selective Toxicity", Methuen and Co , 1968
- 38 C Seshadri, D Suganthan, G Santhkumari and G Y N Iyer, *Indian J Expt Biol* , 1979, **16**, 1187
- 39 S D Seth, Nuhra Johri and K R Sundaram, *Indian J Pharmacol* , 1982, **14**, 207